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INTERNATIONAL ALMANAC

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Фото на обложке / Cover photo: *Polyzonus violaceus* Plavilstshikov, 1933: Lectotype (published by Danilevsky, 2009), male with 6 labels: 1) [red] “Type”; 2) “Yunnan / China”; 3) “Staudinger”; 4) “*Polyzonus / violaceus* m. / N. Plavilstshikov det. / XI.1932”; 5) [red] “LECTOTYPUS / *Polyzonus / VIOLACEUS* / Plavilstshikov, 1933 / M. Danilevsky des., 2008”; 6) [pink] “Зоомузей МГУ (Москва, РОССИЯ) / № ZMMU Col 00088 / Zool. Mus. Mosq. Univ. / (Mosquae, ROSSIA) / ex coll. N. N. Plavilstshikov” - collection of Zoological Museum of the Moscow State University. (photo by M. Lazarev)

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**On the taxonomic rank of *Cerambyx klinzigi* Podaný, 1964
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Cerambycini, Caucasus.

Abstract: The rank of *Cerambyx cerdo klinzigi* Podaný, 1964 is upgraded to species as *Cerambyx klinzigi* Podaný, 1964 following Özdikmen & Turgut (2009). The distinguishing characters and color illustrations are proposed.

Introduction

Cerambyx cerdo klinzigi Podaný, 1964 was described from “Caucase” without exact locality data on the bases of a single peculiar male. Such situation against the backdrop of widespread distribution throughout the whole Caucasus of *C. cerdo acuminatus* Motschulsky, 1853 has given rise to conflicting interpretations of the name in the literature.

***Cerambyx klinzigi* Podaný, 1964**

Figs 1-2

Cerambyx cerdo klinzigi Podaný, 1964: 88 - “Caucase, leg. Leder”; Miroshnikov, 2010: 44 - “Caucase”; Vartanis, 2018: 77 - “Georgia (Caucasus)”; Sláma, 2019: 203 - “Caucasus”.

Cerambyx klinzigi, Özdikmen & Turgut: 2009: 308 - “Caucasus”.

Cerambyx cerdo, Miroshnikov, 2010: 43, 45 (? = *cerdo klinzigi* Podany, 1964), 46-47.

Cerambyx cerdo cerdo, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 159 (= *acuminatus* Motschulsky = *heros* Scopoli, 1763 = *iranicus* Heyrovský, 1951 = *klinzigi* Podaný = *manderstjaernae* Mulsant & Godart, 1855 = *pfisteri* Stierlin, 1864).

Cerambyx [?] *cerdo klinzigi*, Miroshnikov, 2011: 11, 28.

Cerambyx (s. str.) *cerdo acuminatus*, Danilevsky, 2020: 71, 215 (= *klinzigi* Podaný).

Type material. Holotype, male, “Caucase” - Slovenské národné muzeum, Bratislava.

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A single male is known; body rather wide, nearly parallel sided, in *C. cerdo* Linnaeus, 1758 (Fig. 3) body narrow with sides strongly converging posteriorly; male antennae very long, extend beyond elytral apex with three joints; 3rd-5th antennal joints distinctly thicker and shorter, elytral punctation much finer, dots don't conjugate forming vermiform sculpture, elytral veins indistinct, legs thicker, tibiae distinctly curved, spines of elytral apices nearly indistinct; body length: 44 mm, width: 13 mm.

Comments.

Many authors (Podaný, 1964; Miroshnikov, 2010; Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Vartanis, 2018; Sláma, 2019; Danilevsky, 2020) regarded the holotype as unusual representative of *C. cerdo*, but *C. klinzigi* differs by too many systems of characters.

In fact, populations consisting of peculiar specimens of *C. cerdo* are known. According to personal message (2024) by M. Slama, small populations of *C. cerdo cerdo* m. *laevicollis* Heyrovský, 1955 (with smooth pronotum) are known from near Třeboň (Czech Republic) and preserved in the collection of Leopold Seichert. Such populations could be accepted as a geographical form inside subspecies, that is impossible after modern Code of Zoological Nomenclature.

According to Miroshnikov (2010: 46), J. Voříček was personally convinced, that *C. klinzigi* Podaný, 1964 was later described as *C. heinzianus* Demelt, 1976, but Miroshnikov (2010: 46) could not agree with that opinion, and listed several compelling arguments. In fact, *C. heinzianus* is quite a different species. Finally, Miroshnikov (2010: 47) regarded species rank for *C. cerdo klinzigi* as rather probable.

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Fig. 1. *Cerambyx klinzigi* Podaný, 1964: holotype, male, “Caucase” (photo by RNDr. V. Jansky, Slovenské národné múzeum, Bratislava).

Fig. 2. Set of the holotype labels of *Cerambyx cerdo klinzigi* Podaný, 1964 (photos by RNDr. V. Jansky, Slovenské národné múzeum, Bratislava).

Fig. 3. *Cerambyx cerdo acutispinum* Motschulsky, 1853: male, Armenia, Megri, 30.6.2003, M. Danilevsky leg. (collection of M. Danilevsky).

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**Three new *Litargus* Erichson, 1846 species from Peru
(Coleoptera: Mycetophagidae)**

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Key words: Taxonomy, new species, description, Coleoptera, Mycetophagidae, *Litargus*, Peru.

Abstract: The following three new species from Peru are described, illustrated and compared: *Litargus (Litargus) junin* **sp. nov.**, *Litargus (Litargus) hrdlickai* **sp. nov.**, *Litargus (Litargus) peruanus* **sp. nov.** A list of recorded *Litargus* species from Peru is included.

Introduction

The genus *Litargus* Erichson, 1846 can be divided into the following 3 subgenera: *Alitargus* Casey, 1900 including 3 species, *Litargosomus* Motschulsky, 1858 including 20 species, *Litargus* Erichson, 1846 including 16 species. Additionally there are 21 species reported as incertae sedis (Háva 2022, 2023). Two species are known from Peru: *L. (Litargus) tetraspilotus* LeConte, 1856 and *L. (Litargus) arcuatus* Erichson, 1847 (Shepard 2020, Háva 2022).

During the determination of some unidentified material deposited in Naturhistorisches Museum, Wien and the author's collection three new species from Peru were found and are described here.

Material and methods

The material is deposited in the following collections:

JHAC - Jiří Háva, Private Entomological Laboratory & Collection, Únětice u Prahy, Prague-West, Czech Republic;

NHMW - Naturhistorisches Museum, Wien, Austria (M. Seidel).

The size of the beetles or of their body parts can be useful in

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species recognition and thus, the following measurements were made:

total length (TL) - linear distance from anterior margin of head to apex of elytra.

elytral width (EW) - maximum linear transverse distance.

Specimens of the presently described species are provided with red, printed label with text as follows: „HOLOTYPE (or PARATYPE) *name of species* sp. nov. Jiří Háva det. 2023”.

Results

Genus *Litargus* Erichson, 1846

Litargus (Litargus) junin sp. nov.

Figs 1-3

Description. Female. Body measurements TL 2.9 mm, EW 1.7 mm; oblong-oval, weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; brown, covered with brown and and yellow, recumbent setation; elytra brown with patterns covered by yellow setation.

Head brown, with dense and coarse punctures; covered by yellow, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae with 11 antennomeres, light brown (Fig. 3); palpomeres brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

Pronotum brown covered by intermixed brown and yellow setation, convex dorsally, rugose, with large and dense punctures; widest at middle, gradually narrowed anteriorly and posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; lateral sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts.

Scutellum brown, with short recumbent yellow setation.

Elytra dark brown covered by brown recumbent setation, patterns from yellow setation, elongate, subparallel sided, narrowed from apical 1/4 part to apex (Fig. 1). Epipleuron brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation.

Meta-meso ventrite brown, with yellow recumbent setation, finely punctate.

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Legs entirely light brown with light brown spines, covered with brown recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

Abdomen with visible ventrites brown, finely punctate, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Pygidium brown, covered with yellow recumbent setation.

Male. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is similar to *Litargus irregularis* (Sharp, 1902), but differs from it by the broadly oval body, elytral patterns of yellow setation and the structure of the antennae, and from other known Neotropical species by the same characters.

Type material. Holotype (1 ♀): Peru, Junin Reg., Satipo prov., ca 5-6 km above Rio Venado, 11°11'05''S, 74°45'34''W, ca 1300 m, windows trap, 19.1.2019, A. Petrov leg., (NHMW). Paratype (1 ♀): Peru, Junin Reg., Satipo prov., near Rio Venado vill., ca 1122 m, x.2014, (ex ebay), (JHAC).

Etymology. Toponymic, named after the Junin Region in Peru.

Litargus (Litargus) peruanus sp. nov.

Figs 4-5

Description. Female. Body measurements TL 1.8 mm, EW 1.0 mm; oblong-oval; weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; brown, covered with brown recumbent setation; elytra brown with yellow patterns covered by yellow setation.

Head brown, with dense and coarse punctures; covered by yellow, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae from third segment missing, first two segments light brown; palpomeres light brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

Pronotum brown with yellowish lateral parts covered by yellow setation and with large brown spot discally, convex dorsally, rugose, with large and dense punctures, other parts covered with brown recumbent setation; widest at middle, gradually narrowed anteriorly and posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; lateral sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts.

Figs. 1-3. *Litargus (Litargus) junin* sp. nov.: 1 - habitus, dorsal aspect; 2 - habitus, lateral aspect; 3 - antenna.

Figs. 4-5. *Litargus (Litargus) peruanus* sp. nov.: 4 - habitus, dorsal aspect; 5 - habitus, lateral aspect.

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Scutellum small, brown, with short recumbent yellow setation.

Elytra dark brown with yellowish-orange patterns, covered by brown recumbent setation, patterns covered by yellow setation, elongate, subparallel-sided, narrowed from apical 1/4 part to apex (Figs. 4-5). Epipleuron brown, covered with brown recumbent setation.

Meta-meso ventrite brown, with yellow recumbent setation, finely punctate.

Legs entirely light brown with light brown spines, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

Abdomen with visible ventrites light brown, finely punctate, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Pygidium brown, covered with brown recumbent setation.

Male. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The new species differs from other known Neotropical species by the colour of the elytral patterns and the structure of the antennae.

Type material. Holotype (1 ♀): Peru, Junin Reg., Satipo prov., ca 5-6 km above Rio Venado, 11°11'05''S, 74°45'34''W, ca 1300 m, windows trap, 19.1.2019, A. Petrov leg., (MHNW).

Etymology. Toponymic, named for the country of origin.

***Litargus (Litargus) hrdlickai* sp. nov.**

Figs. 6-9

Description. Male. Body measurements TL 2.0 mm, EW 1.1 mm; oblong-oval; weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; brown, covered with brown recumbent setation; elytra brown with orange patterns covered by yellow setation.

Head brown, with dense and coarse punctures; covered by yellow, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae with 11 antennomeres, light brown (Fig. 8); palpi brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

Pronotum brown with orange latero-apical parts covered by yellow setation, rugose, with large and dense punctures, other parts

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covered with brown recumbent setation; widest apically, gradually narrowed anteriorly and posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; lateral sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts.

Scutellum light brown, with short recumbent yellow setation.

Elytra dark brown with orange patterns, covered by brown recumbent setation, patterns covered by yellow setation, elongate, subparallel-sided, narrowed from apical 1/4 part to apex (Figs. 6-7). Epipleuron brown, covered with brown recumbent setation.

Meta-meso ventrite brown, with brown recumbent setation, finely punctate.

Legs entirely light brown with light brown spines, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

Abdomen with visible ventrites light brown, finely punctate, covered with brown recumbent setation. Pygidium brown, covered with brown recumbent setation.

Male genitalia as in Fig. 9.

Female. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The new species differs from other known Neotropical species by the colour of the elytral patterns and the structure of the antennae.

Type material. Holotype (1 ♂): Peru, Junin Reg., Satipo prov., near Rio Venado vill., ca 1122 m, x.2014, (ex ebay), (JHAC).

Etymology. Patronymic, dedicated to my friend Jan Hrdlička (Babice u Říčan, Czech Republic), specialist in Coleoptera, family Carabidae: Brachininae.

LIST OF *LITARGUS* SPECIES RECORDED FROM PERU

Litargus arcuatus Erichson, 1847

= *Litargus quadriarcuatus* (sic!): Shepard, 2020

Litargus hrdlickai sp. nov.

Litargus junin sp. nov.

Litargus peruanus sp. nov.

Litargus tetraspilotus LeConte, 1856

= *Litargus quadrimaculatus* Kirsch, 1873

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Figs. 6-9. *Litargus (Litargus) hrdlickai* sp. nov.: 6- habitus, dorsal aspect; 7- habitus, lateral aspect; 8 - antenna; 9 - male genitalia.

Figs. 10-11. Habitus: 10 - *Litargus tetraspilotus* LeConte, 1856; 11- *Litargus arcuatus* Erichson, 1847 (according to Shepard 2020).

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Taxonomic notes on longhorned beetles with the descriptions of several new taxa (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, zoogeography, new genus, new subgenus, new synonyms, new rank, another subfamily added.

Abstract: Many newly published taxonomy modifications are discussed. Several taxonomy news is proposed.

Introduction.

Many taxonomic publications on Cerambycidae are regularly appear each year without special comments by colleagues. I propose here alternative positions on several questionable cases. Several new synonyms cannot be accepted. Several new names were in fact synonyms. Certain taxonomy acts were not acceptable. Rank of six species names was downgraded to subspecies. A new genus and a new subgenus were proposed, as well as many new synonyms. One old subfamily name was restored, as well as one subspecies name. A wrong geographical record was corrected, as well as some other wrongly published data. Rank of one old name was restored.

1. A new unacceptable tribal system of Lepturinae was proposed by Zamoroka (2022b): Cariliini (*Carilia*, *Acmaeops*, *Gaurotetes*, *Paragaurotetes*, *Dinoptera*, *Gnathacmaeops*, *Cortodera*); Pidoniini (Pidonia, Fallacea), Evodiini (Evodinus, Brachyta). Lepturini includes 6 Palaearctic genera (Anoplodera, Nivellia, Leptura, Anastrangalia, Grammoptera, Strangalia); Stenocorini - 2 (Stenocorus, Anisorus), Rhamnusiini - 3 (Rhamnusium, Akimerus, Enoploderes), Rhagiini - 2 (Pachyta, Rhagium).

Cortodera cannot be in one tribe with all genera around *Dinoptera*; *Rhamnusium*, *Akimerus*, and *Enoploderes* are totally

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different on larval and imaginal characters, so until better decisions it is necessary conserve traditional system of Palaearctic Lepturinae with 7 tribes: Xylosteini, Encyclopini, Oxymirini, Enoploderini, Rhamnusiini, Rhagiini, Lepturini.

2. *Evodinellus borealis* (Gyllenhal, 1827) = *Pidonia petrovi* Danilevsky, 2023a, **syn. nov.** on the base of the type series study.

3. *Megarhagium* Reitter, 1913 and *Hagrium* Villiers, 1978 must be accepted as valid genera names as in Villier (1978).

4. Very different genera *Brachysomida* Casey, 1913 and *Pseudogaurotina* Plavilstshikov, 1958 were inadequately published by Zamoroka (2022b) as subgenera of one genus, and impossible combination was proposed: “*Brachysomida (Pseudogaurotina) excellens*”.

5. According to Zamoroka (2022b), “*Evodinus borealis* does not belong to the separate genus *Evodinellus* Winkler, 1929” or *Evodinus* LeConte, 1850 = *Evodinellus* Plavilstshikov, 1915. But American *Evodinus* differs from *Evodinellus borealis* (Gyllenhal, 1827) by the position of antennal insertions, which are situated in *Evodinellus borealis* in front of anterior eye margins, while in *Evodinus* antennal insertions disposed behind the line connecting anterior eye margins.

6. The names of very different genera: *Acmaeops* LeConte, 1850 and *Euracmaeops* Danilevsky, 2014 were wrongly published by Zamoroka (2022b) as synonyms.

7. Wrong synonyms were accepted by Zamoroka (2022a):

“*Cortodera flavimana* (Waltl, 1838) = *C. moldovana* Danilevsky, 1995”. In fact, *C. moldovana* has no connection with *C. flavimana*, but close to *C. tibialis* (Marseul, 1876), and especially to *C. tibialis rossica* Danilevsky, 2001b. No evidences of the presence of *C. flavimana* and *C. moldovana* in Ukraine exist.

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8. *Cornumutilla quadrivittata* (Gebler, 1830) was wrongly recorded for Ukraine by Zamoroka (2018, 2022a). *C. quadrivittata* is widely distributed in Siberia (Lazarev, 2009) and does not penetrate to Europe. A single record for Moscow Region was very doubtful. Only *C. lineata* (Letzner, 1844) is distributed in Europe.

9. *Pedostrangalia revestita corsica* Vartanis, 2024b, **stat. nov.** was described from France (Corsica) as a species on the bases of red anterior legs in combination with black other legs. No other features are observed that distinguish the new taxon from *P. r. revestita*.

10. The reality of two different subgenera of *Stictoleptura* [*Paracorymbia* sensu Miroshnikov, 2021, 2016] subgen. *Batesiata* Miroshnikov, 1998 and *S.* subgen. *Pyrrholeptura* Lazarev, 2016 was not accepted by Miroshnikov (2016, 2021). I insist on three fundamental differences: *Pyrrholeptura* is characterized by red elytral color, shallow male abdominal emargination and dense elytral punctation. The difference in color between two subgenera can't be denied, but Miroshnikov shows several examples of different taxa where elytral color is not important. Such reasoning is irrelevant. He shows male abdominal emargination in both species, but the shape of those structures in his photos is distinctly different, as well as elytral punctation in his photos of “*P. (Batesiata) tesserula*” and “*P. (B.) pyrrha*”. So, *Stictoleptura (Batesiata)* Miroshnikov, 1998 and *S. (Pyrrholeptura)* Lazarev, 2016 are good valid names.

11. *Stictoleptura (Maculileptura)* Danilevsky, 2014) was not accepted by Miroshnikov (2021) who did not see the differences of this taxon from *Paracorymbia* (s. str.) Miroshnikov, 1998. But that valid name was established by Danilevsky (2014) instead of *Paracorymbia* (s. str.) «group *maculicornis*» Miroshnikov (1998). All characters of the group were published by Miroshnikov (1998: 594): Last abdominal male sternite with shallow, narrow, short, but well distinct impression, slightly emarginated apically; hind male tibiae not curved, with two apical spines; elytra yellowish, monochrome or with dark apex and lateral margin; antennal joints with light bases or with light rings.

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12. Several new synonyms are proposed: *Xylotrechus* (*Xylotrechus* Chevrolat, 1860 = *Fulvotrechus* Zamoroka, 2021 = *Hieroglyphotrechus* Zamoroka, 2021 = *Ignetrechus* Zamoroka, 2021 = **syn. nn.**), *Xylotrechus* Chevrolat, 1860 = *Spinotrechus* Zamoroka, 2021, **syn. nov.**

In general Zamoroka's publications were often based on molecular data, but strong morphological argument were usually ignored. For example, such cases as one tribe for so different genera as *Rhamnusium*, *Akimerus* and *Enoploderes*, as well as joining of *Rutpela maculata* (Poda von Neuhaus, 1761) and *Stenurella nigra* (Linnaeus, 1758) inside one genus show complete absurdity of his method.

13. Wrong synonyms proposed by Zamoroka (2021): *Xylotrechus* = *Rusticoclytus* must be rejected, and valid name *Xylotrechus* (*Rusticoclytus* Vives, 1977) generally accepted (Vives, 1977, 2000; Villiers, 1978, 1979; Demelt, 1982; Bílý & Mehl, 1989; Marquet, 2001, 2015; Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007; Sama, 2008; Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Danilevsky, 2012, 2020; Alekseev & Maryutin, 2019; Stolbov et al., 2019; Trócoli, 2019; Gradinarov & Sivilov, 2020; Sakalian et al., 2020 and others) must be preserved.

14. *Xyloclytus* was wrongly upgraded to genus rank by Zamoroka (2021). Valid subgenus name *Xylotrechus* (*Xyloclytus* Reitter, 1913) must be preserved.

15. *Teratoclytus* D.W. Zaitzev, 1937 cannot be moved to Anaglyptini, as it was proposed by Zamoroka (2021) and must be returned to Clytini (elytral bases without tubercles).

16. *Humeromaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011: 537 (type species *Cerambyx figuratus* Scopoli, 1763) was introduced as a subgenus of *Chlorophorus*. It was upgraded to genus level by Zamoroka (2021) without sufficient reasons. *Sparganophorus* Zamoroka, 2021 (type species *Clytus diadema* Motschulsky, 1854) was described for a single species, which was placed by Özdikmen (2022) in *Ch. (Humeromaculatus)*, so *Ch. (Humeromaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011 = *Sparganophorus* Zamoroka, 2021, **syn. nov.**

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17. *Perderomaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011: 537 (type species *Cerambyx sartor* Müller, 1766) was upgraded by Zamoroka (2021) to genus level without sufficient reasons, the valid name must be *Chlorophorus* (*Perderomaculatus*).

18. *Chlorophorus* (*Viridiphorus* Zamoroka, 2021, type species: *Callidium herbstii* Brahm, 1790) = *Chlorophorus* (*Brevenotatus* Özdikmen, 2022, type species: *Clytus distinguendus* Perroud, 1855), **syn. nov.** as *Ch. herbstii* was included in *Ch. (Brevenotatus)*.

19. New synonyms must be accepted:

Stenurella (*Priscostenurella* Özdikmen, 2013) = *Rutpela* (*Eduardvivesia* Zamoroka, Trócoli, Shparyk & Semaniuk, 2022) = *Rutpela* (*Nigromacularia* Zamoroka, Trócoli, Shparyk & Semaniuk, 2022), **syn. nn.**

20. *Ropalopus hungaricus olympicus* Vartanis, 2024c was described as *R. insubricus olympicus* Vartanis, 2024c from Greece (Olympos Mt., Pieria prov., 700-1000 m), and *R. hungaricus creticus* Vartanis, 2024c was described as a species from Crete.

21. *Chlorophorus* cannot be separated from Clytini, so Clytini Mulsant, 1839 = Chlorophorini Zamoroka, 2021, **syn. nov.**

22. Three new combinations were incorrectly accepted by Zamoroka et. al. (2022): *Rutpela* (*Eduardvivesia*) *vaucheri* (Bedel, 1900), *R. (Nigrostenurella) nigra* (Linnaeus, 1758), *R. (Nigromacularia) septempunctata* (Fabricius 1793). All three taxa must be left in *Stenurella* as: *S. (Priscostenurella) vaucheri*, *S. (P.) septempunctata* and *S. (Nigrostenurella) nigra*.

Several species were placed by Zamoroka et. al. (2022) in wrong subgenera: *Stenurella* (*Priscostenurella*) *jaegeri* (Hummel, 1825), *S. (P.) novercalis* (Reitter, 1901), *S. (s. str.) hybridula* (Reitter, 1902), *S. (s. str.) approximans* (Rosenhauer, 1856). Must be: *S. (Stenurelloides) jaegeri*, *S. (S.) novercalis*, *S. (Iberostenurella) hybridula*, *S. (Crassostenurella) approximans*.

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23. *Oxypleurus nodieri* Mulsant, 1839 was placed by Zamoroka (2022a) in Atimiini without sufficient reasons. The species belongs to Saphanini as it is generally accepted.

24. Wrong synonyms were accepted by Zamoroka (2022a):

“*Tetropium fuscum* (Fabricius, 1787) = *T. tauricum* Shapovalov, 2007”. The holotype of *T. tauricum* strongly differs from many hundreds of known *T. fuscum*. Up to now only very peculiar holotype of *T. tauricum* is known. So, rather probably it was just a teratic specimen of local species - *T. castaneum* (Linnaeus, 1758). According to Plavilstshikov (1940), *T. fuscum* was not collected in Crimea. *T. castaneum* only was recorded for Crimean fauna by Zagaikevich (1991: 153). In fact *T. fuscum* is absent in Crimea. It was only recorded by Bartenev (2009) with question mark on the base of WEB European Cerambycidae list of 2000 by M.L. Danilevsky.

25. *Anoplistes balcanicus* Sláma, 2010 described from Bulgaria was wrongly published as a subspecies of *A. halodendri* (Pallas, 1773) by Danilevsky (2020) on the bases of the records by Muraj (1960) of *Purpuricenus ephippium* for Albania. *Asias ephippium* was also recorded for Bulgaria by Angelov (1995) and for Rumania by Panin, Săvulescu (1961). But in fact, *Anoplistes balcanicus* Sláma, 2010 does not similar to *A. halodendri* because of short antenna and legs, peculiar elytral design. So, *Anoplistes balcanicus* Sláma, 2010 must be accepted as a valid species name, as it was originally introduced. The presence of *Anoplistes halodendri* in Balcan area rests rather doubtful.

26. *Plagionotus detritus caucasicola* Plavilstshikov, 1940 = *P. d. grecus* Vartanis, 2023, **syn. nov.**

Plagionotus detritus caucasicola Plavilstshikov, 1940 was described with two taxonomy rank in the original publication: as “m.” [morpha] and as “форма” [forma]. The later makes the name available, and it was generally accepted (Özdikmen & Turgut, 2009; Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Danilevsky, 2010; Özdikmen, 2014; Vitali, 2016; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2018; Lazarev, 2019; Danilevsky, 2020; Vartanis, 2023 and others).

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Vartanis (2023) accepted *P. d. caucasicola* Plavilstshikov, 1940 as a valid name, but proposed no distinguishing characters. In fact, the Caucasian populations are just identic to Greece populations. Populations from Peloponnesus were described by Vartanis (2023) and I've got good series from Northern Greece (Thessaly): 7 males, 8 females from Ossa Mt. and 1 male, 2 females from near Kalabaka (Metora). Greece specimens are also rather pale as specimens from Caucasian populations, have same wide yellow pronotum anteriorly, wide yellow elytral stripes, and posterior elytral stripes are partly or totally conjugated.

Acronyms of collections:

MD - collection of M. Danilevsky (Moscow)

ML - collection of M. Lazarev (Moscow)

SM - collection of S. Murzin (Moscow)

ZMM - collection of Zoological Museum of the Moscow State University

***Plagionotus detritus caucasicola* Plavilstshikov, 1940**

Figs. 1-3

Type locality. Russia, Republic of Adygea, Maykop environs (on the bases of lectotype designation).

Description. Dark areas of pronotum and elytra rather light-brown; elytra with widened transverse yellow stripes behind middle, dark stripes in between very narrow; anterior pronotal yellow area very wide, often joined with central transverse pronotal stripe; narrow yellow transverse stripe behind elytral bases more or less reduced or totally absent; body length: 14.3-17.5 mm.

P. d. detritus (Linnaeus, 1758) is characterized by dark-brown ground color of elytra and pronotum; light central pronotal stripe usually well developed; yellow elytral stripes usually very narrow; body length: 10-19 mm (Plavilstshikov, 1940).

Material. Lectotype (Figs 1-2) designated by Danilevsky (2009), published by Lazarev (2019), male (length: 14.0 mm; width: 4.2 mm) with 4 labels: 1) "Cauc. occ. bor. / Maikop / 25.V.[1]928"; 2) "ex coll. Shaposhnikov"; 3) [red] "LECTOTYPUS / *Plagionotus detritus* / forma CAUCASICOLA / Plavilstshikov, 1940 / M. Danilevsky des., 2008"; 4) [pink] "Зоомузей МГУ (Москва,

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РОССИЯ) / № ZMMU Col 00180 / Zool. Mus. Mosq. Univ. / (Mosquae, ROSSIA) / ex coll. N. N. Plavilstshikov” - ZMM; Paralectotype (Fig. 3): 1 female, Maykop, 5.6.1935 - ZMM.

Additional materials. 1 male, Krasnodar Reg., L’vovskaya, 16.6.1966 - ZMM; 1 female, Ekaterinodar, 9.7.1914, Lyutkovsky - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Stavropol, V. Lutshnik - ZMM; 1 male, Armenia, Dilizhan, 5000’, 26.7.1934, N. Plavilstshikov - ZMM; 1 female, Transcauc., Kars - ZMM; 1 male, Krasnodar, Novopokhladnoe, 13.6.1956-1959 - MD; 1 female, Sochi, Lazarevskoe, 4.8.1983, A. Koval - MD; 1 male, Krasnodar, Ubinskoe, 10.5.1976, M. Kravchenko - MD; 1 male, Krasnodar, Ubinskoe, 2.5.1991, A. Abramov - MD; 1 male, Krasnodar, Ubinskoe, 5.8.1976, Belov - ML; 1 male, Krasnodar, Novopokhladnoe, 25.5.1959 - MD;. 3 males (Fig. 4), 4 females (Fig. 5), Ossa Mt. (East), VII.2001, P. Tauzin - ML; 4 males, 4 females, with the same label - SM; 1 male, 2 females, 1-2 km N Kalabaka, Meteora, VI, 1981, M. Sláma - ML.

Distribution. Russia, North Caucasus, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran, Turkey; Greece (Thessaly, Peloponnesus); the records for Syria (Plavilstshikov, 1940; Danilevsky, 2020; Vartanis, 2023) were most probably connected with *P. detritus africaeseptentrionalis* Tippmann, 1952.

27. *Dorcadion fulvum erythropterum* Fischer von Waldheim, 1823 = *Dorcadion fulvum opillicum* Zamoroka, 2019, **syn. nov.** Big available series of the species (including series from “Opillya” - geographic region of the Podolian Upland in Lvov Oblast, Ivano-Frankovsk Oblast and Ternopol Oblast in western Ukraine) show a great degree of geographical variability masking local forms.

28. *Dorcadion fulvum heracles* Vartanis, 2024a, **stat. nov.** was described from Greece (Olympus Mt., Pieria prov.) as a species on the bases of black first antennal joint and black anterior legs. No other features are observed that distinguish the new taxon from *D. f. fulvum* (Scopoli, 1763).

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29. The new wrong synonyms were published by Zamoroka (2022a): without analyses of corresponding materials and with false statement: “ranges of some of them completely overlap”. “*Dorcadion cinerarium cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787) = *D. c. macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932 = *D. c. zubovi* Lazarev, 2011”, “*D. c. panticapaeum* Plavilstshikov, 1951 = *D. c. bartenevi* Lazarev, 2011 = *D. c. skrylniki* Lazarev, 2011 = *D. c. azovense* Lazarev, 2011 = *D. c. gorodinskii* Danilevsky, 1996 = *D. c. demidovi* Danilevsky, 2013 = *D. c. mosyakini* Danilevsky, 2021”; “*Dorcadion equestre* (Laxmann, 1770) = *D. e. vadimi* Danilevsky, 2021”; “*Dorcadion holosericeum* Krynicki, 1832 = *D. h. ustinovi* Danilevsky, 2021”. Most probably Zamoroka did not know such specimens, so, valid names must be preserved: *D. c. macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932; *D. c. zubovi* Lazarev, 2011; *D. c. bartenevi* Lazarev, 2011; *D. c. skrylniki* Lazarev, 2011; *D. c. azovense* Lazarev, 2011; *D. c. gorodinskii* Danilevsky, 1996; *D. c. demidovi* Danilevsky, 2013; *D. c. mosyakini* Danilevsky, 2021; *D. e. vadimi* Danilevsky, 2021; *D. h. ustinovi* Danilevsky, 2021.

30. The wrong synonyms *Falsomesosella truncatipennis* Pic, 1944 = *F. taibaishana* Lazarev, 2021 published by Lin, Weigel & Ge (2021), can't be accepted, as holotype of *F. truncatipennis* (depicted by Lin et al., 2021) from Zhejiang (see Lin, 2015) is distinctly wider with more elongated prothorax, besides its type area is strongly distant. So, *F. taibaishana* Lazarev, 2021 is a valid name.

31. *Quasimesosella ussuriensis* was recorded by Danilevsky (2023b: 334) for the south of Khabarovsk Region (Listvyanaya River), but according to personal communication by N. Anisimov (November, 2023), that record must be connected with Listvenichnaya River from Malyi Khingan in Jewish Autonomous Republic. The record of that species for Duchin must be connected with Dichun River south-eastwards Radde (Jewish Autonomous Republic).

32. *Paratetrops* **gen. nov.**

Type species. *Tetrops warncke* Holzschuh, 1977.

Description. Body densely covered with long thick black erect setae; antennae extremely sick, with apical joints about as long as wide;

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pronotum with smooth central stripe; elytra with rough big punctation. A single species distributed in south Turkey is known - *Paratetrops warncke* (Holzschuh, 1977), **new rank**.

Etymology. close to *Tetrops*. Gender masculine.

33. *Tetrops peterkai* Scořepa, 2020 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Tetrops praeustus peterkai* Scořepa, 2020, **stat. nov.**; type locality: Czech Republic, Moravia, Horní Pole environs.

According to the original description the species is distributed in Czech Republic, Slovakia, Austria, Germany.

34. *Tetrops praetermitus* Sláma, 2020a is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Tetrops praeustus praetermitus* Sláma, 2020, **stat. nov.**; type locality. Bohemia, Lásenice. According to Sláma (2020b) the taxon is distributed in South Bohemia only.

35. *Phytoecia (Musaria) rubropunctata* (Goeze 1777) was wrongly recorded for Ukraine by Zamoroka (2022a). It is a West European species absent in Ukraine; it does not penetrate east of Germany (Bense, 1995; Sama, 2003), but was recently recorded for Spain, France and Italy only (Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Danilevsky, 2020). Old wrong published records could be based on specimens of *Ph. (M.) argus* (Frölich, 1793) or *Ph. (M.) faldermanni* (Faldermann, 1837).

36. A new subgenus *Phytoecia (Danilevskia)* **subgen. nov.**, type species: *Saperda molybdaena* Dalman, 1817) is proposed for 4 species: *Ph. (Danilevskia) molybdaena* (Dalman, 1817), *Ph. (Danilevskia) uncinata* (W. Redtenbacher, 1842), *Ph. (Danilevskia) tenuilinea* Fairmaire, 1876 and *Ph. (Danilevskia) badenkoi* Danilevsky, 1988. The new taxon is characterized by the absence of the dense solid elytral scaly cover consisting of small scales or very short setae. Such cover is typical for *Ph. (Opsilia)* Mulsant, 1862). Besides all *Ph. (Danilevskia)* has unicuspid mandibulae and eyes with joined dorsal and ventral lobes. New subgenus name is feminine. The name is dedicated to Mikhail Leontievich Danilevsky - a specialist on Palaearctic Cerambycidae and my constant colleague.

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37. Up to now Palaearctic Cerambycidae includes 8 subfamilies (Parandrinae, Prioninae, Lepturinae, Necydalinae, Spondylidinae, Apatophyseinae, Cerambycinae, Lamiinae). Now another one must be accepted: Agapanthiinae Mulsant, 1839 (type genus *Agapanthia* Audinet-Serville, 1835, monobasic), which was traditionally included in Lamiinae.

Agapanthiinae is characterized by moderately or small body size; usually strongly elongated; parallel sided or with sides slightly diverging posteriorly; antennae usually long, often much longer than body, usually 12-segmented (in *Pseudocalamobius* - 11-segmented); frons usually sloping backwards; prothorax always without lateral spines or tubercles; legs short; anterior coxae spherical; claws simple, divergent, without tooth-like appendages or denticles; metepisternae very narrow, parallel sided. Larvae with cylindrical "C"-like curved body, without legs; head slightly elongated, strongly prominent; abdominal ventral ampullae partly reduced.

Agapanthiinae differ from Lamiinae by many larval characters: "C"-like curved body, slightly elongated head, rounded laterally, ventral ampullae partly or totally reduced.

38. *Agapanthia kindermanni* Pic, 1905 must be returned to the original subspecies rank as *Agapanthia dahli kindermanni* Pic, 1905.

39. *Agapanthia lateralis* Ganglbauer, 1884 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Agapanthia dahli lateralis* Ganglbauer, 1884, **stat. nov.**

40. *Agapanthia mutinensium* Sama & Rapuzzi, 2010 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Agapanthia dahli mutinensium* Sama & Rapuzzi, 2010, **stat. nov.**

41. *Agapanthia pustulifera* Pic, 1905 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Agapanthia dahli pustulifera* Pic, 1905, **stat. nov.**

42. *Agapanthia salviae* Holzschuh, 1975 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Agapanthia dahli salviae* Holzschuh, 1975, **stat. nov.**

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43. *Agapanthia schurmanni* Sama, 1979 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Agapanthia dahli schurmanni* Sama, 1979, **stat. nov.**

44. *Agapanthia subsimplicicornis* Sama & Rapuzzi, 2010 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Agapanthia dahli subsimplicicornis* Sama & Rapuzzi, 2010, **stat. nov.**

45. Zaitzev D.W. (original spelling - Zaitzev 1931, 1937) was wrongly published several times (Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Danilevsky, 2020) as Zaitzev D.A. The original spelling was unacceptably changed by Zamoroka (2021) to “Zajciw”.

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Figs 1-5. *Plagionotus detritus caucasicola* Plavilstshikov, 1940:
1. Lectotype, male; 2. Lectotype labels; 3. Paralectotype, female, Maykop,
5.6.1935; 4. Male, Ossa Mt. (East), VII.2001, P. Tausin;
5. Female with the same label.

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